

A Diagnostic Unified Classification Model for Classifying Multi-Sized and Multi-Modal Brain Graphs Using Graph Alignment

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Abstract

-Background. Presence of multimodal brain graphs derived from different neuroimaging modalities is inarguably one of the most critical challenges in building *unified* classification models that can be trained and tested on *any* brain graph regardless of its size and the modality it was derived from.

-Existing methods. One solution is to learn a model for each modality independently, which is cumbersome and becomes more time-consuming as the number of modalities increases. Another traditional solution is to build a model inputting multimodal brain graphs for the target prediction task; however, this is only applicable to datasets where *all* samples have joint neuro-modalities.

-New method. In this paper, we propose to build a unified brain graph classification model trained on unpaired multimodal brain graphs, which can classify *any brain graph of any size*. This is enabled by incorporating a graph alignment step where all multi-modal graphs of different sizes and heterogeneous distributions are mapped to a common template graph. Next, we design a graph alignment strategy to the target fixed-size template and further apply linear discriminant analysis (LDA) to the aligned graphs as a supervised dimensionality reduction technique for the target classification task.

-Results. We tested our method on unpaired autistic and healthy brain connectomes derived from functional and morphological MRI datasets (two

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modalities).

-Conclusion. Our results showed that our unified model method not only has great promise in solving such a challenging problem but achieves comparable performance to models trained on each modality independently.

Keywords: Multi-modal brain connectome classification, multi-sized brain graph alignment, graph node embedding, linear discriminant analysis, neurological disorder diagnosis

1. Introduction

Multimodal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has introduced new exciting opportunities for understanding the brain as a complex system of interacting units in both health and disease. Based on MRI data, the brain can be represented as a connectome (i.e., graph), where the connection between different anatomical regions of interest (ROIs) is modeled. A large body of research work showed how the brain connectome gets altered by neurological and neuropsychiatric disorders, such as dementia and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (Fornito et al., 2015; Van den Heuvel and Sporns, 2019). In network neuroscience (Bassett and Sporns, 2017), the brain connectome, which is typically regarded as a graph encoding the relationships between pairs of ROIs, presents a macroscale representation of the interactions between anatomical regions at *functional, structural or morphological levels*, derived from different multimodal MRI (e.g., functional resting-state MRI or T1-weighted MRI) (Bassett and Sporns, 2017). A bulk of connectome analysis studies used single modality to design unimodal machine learning frameworks for examining and classifying unimodal brain connectomes (Bi et al., 2018; Lidaka, 2014; Chen et al., 2011a; Du et al., 2018; Cheng and Liu, 2017; Chen et al., 2011b; Andersen et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015). For instance, a recent Kaggle competition paper (Bilgen et al., 2020) investigated the potential of cortical morphological networks in distinguishing between autistic and healthy subjects using different machine learning frameworks. Notably, single modality brain connectivity presents a reductionist view of the complexity of the brain construct, whereas multi-modal connectomic data provides complementary and more integral representations of the brain, which can be leveraged for designing learners trained on *paired* samples (i.e., each sample should have the same number of connectomic modalities) (Mesrob et al., 2012; Calhoun and Sui, 2016).

Although multi-modal brain connectomes present a rich dataset to design computer-aided diagnosis models; however, with their variation in resolution (i.e., connectome size or number of brain ROIs), heterogeneity, and lack of parity of samples across modalities, they can present several barriers to building learning-based classification models. In fact, it is not possible to train a conventional classification model (e.g., support vector machines) on such incoherent multimodal datasets in terms of the number of feature across samples. As an alternative solution, one can train a unimodal classifier on each modality, independently. However, this overlooks the complementarity and richness of multimodal connectomes and becomes more time-consuming as the number of modalities increases. Another solution is to combine different multimodal connectomes in the given population by simple concatenation and then train a single classifier using the concatenated feature vectors (Dai and He, 2014; Schouten et al., 2016; Raeper et al., 2018; Graa and Rekik, 2019; Corps and Rekik, 2019). However, such approach requires *paired* samples across modalities, i.e., all MRI modalities should be available for each subject in the population. This wastefully discards existing incomplete multimodal MRI data as well as independent datasets collected from different sources with varying numbers of samples and available modalities.

To address these limitations, we propose a unified classification model for classifying multi-sized and multi-modal brain graphs using graph alignment (**Figure 1**). By aligning brain graphs from different modalities to a common template graph, we aim not only to eliminate the size problem we encounter in training a single model, but also avert to learn multiple classification models for multi-modal brain graphs. Our method does not stipulate sample parity across modalities since the multi-modal data are collectively mapped to fixed-size graphs via a shared template regardless of the number of available multimodal brain graphs (i.e., each subject can have one or more modalities).

Drawing inspiration from the recent work (Bai et al., 2019) on transforming arbitrary-sized graphs drawn from *a single modality (i.e., source)* into fixed-sized aligned grid structures for training deep learning models, we further extend it to handle multi-source heterogeneous connectomic datasets using four main steps: (i) extraction of feature vector embeddings using two different strategies: depth-based representation of each node in all brain graphs based on their local neighborhoods (Bai et al., 2019) and graph-wave node embeddings via diffusion wavelets (Donnat et al., 2018), (ii) clustering feature vectors into n_t clusters, each of which represents a node in the tem-

plate graph to estimate, (iii) alignment of each graph from all modalities to the target template graph, and (iv) training a linear classifier using the fixed-sized aligned brain graphs. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to use a unified model for brain disorder classification on multi-modal data using depth-based alignment and presents several contributions. *First*, the proposed method can use any brain graph of any size derived from any neuroimaging modality in brain disease classification. *Second*, we do not need to build multiple classifiers for multi-modal data, but a unified classifier using aligned graphs. *Third*, multi-modal data do not have to be paired. Each available modality may include different number of brain networks collected from different cohorts. *Fourth*, our model can also handle data imbalance problem as the small sample size of a class (e.g., disordered) in one modality can be compensated with the large sample size of the same class in another modality. Our key contributions can be summarized as follows:

- **Methodological.** We pioneered a unified classification model for classifying multi-modal brain graphs with varying sizes using depth-based alignment to a unified connective template, which eliminates the need to build multiple learners for different modalities and does not require paired graphs across modalities.
- **Clinical.** This develops the field of network neuroscience along the joint multi-source multi-modal data analysis front aiming to present a unified model for classifying disorders.

Remark: We set out to solve a challenging classification problem comprising multiple sub-problems. Solving them independently will certainly have a higher classification accuracy; however, our goal is to build a *unified diagnostic framework* that can be used with any modality of any size at any time point within the clinical routine. Simply put, our unified classification model is *diagnostic* while being *agnostic* to the connectomic data source and size, which makes it scalable and generalizable to different diagnostic clinical frameworks.

2. Proposed method

Problem statement. Let $\mathbb{G} = \{\mathcal{G}_1, \dots, \mathcal{G}_M\}$ denote M training connectomic modalities (i.e., multimodal datasets), where each $\mathcal{G}_m = \{\mathbf{G}_m^1, \dots, \mathbf{G}_m^{N_m}\}$ denotes a set of N_m brain connectivity matrices of size $n_m \times n_m$ derived from

Figure 1: Comparison of conventional and proposed classification strategies. (A) Conventional strategy. For each modality, we need to train an independent classification model due to variation in connectome and sample size. (B) Proposed strategy. All multimodal connectomes are first aligned to a fixed template graph, and then a unified classification model is trained on the new fixed-sized aligned connectomes.

neuroimaging modality m (e.g., functional or structural) with a set of brain states (e.g., healthy and disordered) $s \in \mathcal{S}$ to classify. Our goal is to design a unified classification model that can be trained on the dataset \mathbb{G} supervised by the brain state labels available in all datasets, and which can be tested on any brain connectome of size and modality in \mathbb{G} . The proposed solution is based on learning to align all *multi-modal* and *multi-sized* brain graphs in \mathbb{G} to a predefined fixed-size template \mathcal{T} , thereby producing a new set of aligned same-sized brain connectomes $\bar{\mathcal{G}}$.

Figure 2 illustrates the key steps of our framework with depth-based representations (DB) comprising: 1) extraction of depth-based vector representations from each brain graph, 2) clustering depth-based representations and construction of the alignment template, 3) alignment of original multi-modal brain connectomes using correspondence matrices, 4) training a unified classification model using the aligned brain graphs for classifying brain states (e.g., disordered versus healthy). On the other hand, Figure 3 illustrates a similar scenario but while replacing the depth-based brain connectome representation with a graph-wave (GW) representation (i.e., feature vector

representing one subject). Table 1 shows the mathematical notations that will be used throughout the paper.

Before explaining the phases of the proposed method, it is worth noting that there exists a slight difference in the implementation of DB- and GW-based alignments in steps 2 and 3. In DB-based alignment, for each P depth level, we construct depth-specific correspondence matrices for all graphs, align the original graphs according to the estimated correspondence matrices and finally average, for each subject, the resulting aligned matrices across all depths to get the final aligned graphs, whereas graph-wave based alignment involves a single correspondence matrix extraction and graph alignment without depth levels. Therefore alignment procedure is made once for each graph which does not require graph averaging. The classification step following the graph alignment is the same in both cases.

2.1. Extraction of connectomic feature vectors

This first step can be done with two different methods, e.g., creating DB or GW node embedding for each brain graph. Each method has a partially different implementation in steps 2 and 3, which names the overall alignment procedure: DB based graph alignment and GW based graph alignment. In the next step, we will use the obtained feature vectors (e.g., DB or GW) for clustering all nodes in all multimodal connectomes in \mathbb{G} .

Depth-based (DB) representation vectors. To align M different connectomic modalities, each with a N_m connectomes of dimension $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times n_m}$, where $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, to a common template graph \mathcal{T} of $\mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$, we first extract depth-based vector representations (DB) from each node in all graphs based on local neighborhoods (Bai et al., 2019). These representations reflect not only the local structure of nodes, but also how similar they are to each other in terms of connectivity. However, to analyze the local structure of graphs in a proper manner, we need to consider all subgraphs rooted at each node with different depth levels p , providing more refined local features for our target alignment step. Specifically, for each node v in modality m , we find a P dimensional vector that captures its intrinsic topological properties. We denote the depth-based vector representation vector of node v as $\delta(v)$, which can be regarded as a function of nodes. The p -th element in vector $\delta(v)$ encodes the Shannon entropy of the i^{th} graph $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}$ in modality m and at depth p associated with the steady state of the random walk, where $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}$ is the subgraph rooted at node v in modality m limited with the depth p (Bai et al., 2019). $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}$ is composed of nodes that have a shortest path length less

Figure 2: Key steps of the proposed unified classification model with DB feature vectors for classifying multi-sized and multi-modal brain graphs. **1)** Extraction of depth-based representation vectors. For each connectomic modality $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, we first generate P dimensional depth-based representations (DB) of all graphs based on local structure of nodes and concatenate them vertically across all subjects $n = n_1 + \dots + n_M$ across all modalities to get a single depth-based matrix Δ . **2)** Clustering DB vectors and construction of correspondence matrices for multimodal connectome alignment. For each depth value $p \in \{1, \dots, P\}$, we cluster all nodes in multi-modal graphs using first p columns of Δ and construct associated correspondence matrices that encode which nodes to be assigned to which cluster centroids, using DB's of each modality (thick purple arrows). **3)** Alignment of multi-sized multi-modal brain connectomes to a fixed connectome template. For each depth value p and related correspondence matrices (i.e., extracted at depth- p), we align the original multi-modal graphs (thick orange arrows) to \mathcal{T}^p , where \mathcal{T}^p denotes a graph template constructed at depth- p . **4)** Unified classification model. Finally, we construct a unified classification model using LDA trained on the aligned graphs while leveraging the learned templates in each class (e.g., healthy or disordered) to select the most discriminative connections between brain states.

Figure 3: Key steps of the proposed unified classification model with GW feature vectors for classifying multi-sized and multi-modal brain graphs. **1)** Extraction of graph-wave feature vectors. For each connectomic modality $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, we first generate P dimensional graph-wave feature embeddings of all graphs based on local structure of nodes via diffusion wavelets and concatenate them vertically across all subjects $n = n_1 + \dots + n_M$ across all modalities to get a single graph-wave matrix Δ . **2)** Clustering GW vectors and construction of correspondence matrices for multimodal connectome alignment. We cluster all nodes in multi-modal graphs using P dimensional Δ matrix and construct associated correspondence matrices that encode which nodes to be assigned to which cluster centroids, using GW's of each modality (thick purple arrows). **3)** Alignment of multi-sized multi-modal brain connectomes to a fixed connective template. For each related correspondence matrices (i.e., extracted for modality- m), we align the original multi-modal graphs (thick orange arrows) to \mathcal{T} , where \mathcal{T} denotes a graph template. **4)** Unified classification model. Finally, we construct a unified classification model using LDA trained on the aligned graphs while leveraging the learned templates in each class (e.g., healthy or disordered) to select the most discriminative connections between brain states.

Table 1: *Mathematical notations used in the paper.*

Mathematical notation	Definition
M	total number of modality
m	m -th neuroimaging modality (i.e, image source), $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$
N_m	number of brain graphs in modality- m
N	total number of brain graphs from all modalities, $N = (N_1 + \dots + N_m)$
n_m	number of regions of interest (ROIs) or nodes in a graph of modality- m
n_t	number of cluster centroids or number of nodes in template graphs \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{T}^p
P	dimension of extracted feature embeddings or total number of depth levels for subgraph expansion in DB based alignment
p	p -th depth level for subgraph expansion, $p \in \{1, \dots, P\}$
\mathbb{G}	set of all available graphs from M modalities, $\mathbb{G} = \{\mathcal{G}_1, \dots, \mathcal{G}_M\}$
\mathcal{G}_m	set of N_m brain graphs in modality- m , $\mathcal{G}_m = \{\mathbf{G}_m^1, \dots, \mathbf{G}_m^{N_m}\}$
\mathbf{G}_m^i	i -th graph in \mathcal{G}_m
$\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^i$	node- v of \mathbf{G}_m^i
$\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}$	subgraph rooted at node $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^i$ associated with depth- p , $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p} \subseteq \mathbf{G}_m^i$
$\delta(v)$	extracted P -dimensional feature embedding (i.e, DB or GW) for node- v of a graph
Δ	vertically stacked $\delta(v)$ features for nodes of all graphs across all modalities
\mathcal{T}	template graph of $\mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$ in GW based alignment
\mathcal{T}^p	template graph of $\mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$ associated with depth- p in DB based alignment
A	Distance (Dissimilarity) Matrix
\mathbb{C}	set of all corresponding matrices of M modalities, $\mathbb{C} = \{\mathcal{C}_1, \dots, \mathcal{C}_M\}$
\mathcal{C}_m	$\mathcal{C}_m = \{\mathbf{C}_m^1, \dots, \mathbf{C}_m^{N_m}\}$ set of N_m correspondence matrices of \mathcal{G}_m in GW based alignment
\mathbf{C}_m^i	the i -th corresponding matrix in \mathcal{C}_m of \mathbf{G}_m^i in GW based alignment
\mathbf{C}_m^p	$\mathbf{C}_m^p = \{\mathbf{C}_m^{1,p}, \dots, \mathbf{C}_m^{N_m,p}\}$ set of N_m correspondence matrices of \mathcal{G}_m in DB based alignment
$\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p}$	the i -th corresponding matrix in \mathbf{C}_m^p associated with depth- p in DB based alignment
$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^p$	set of N_m aligned graphs of modality- m with respect to depth- p in DB based alignment
$\bar{\mathbf{G}}^p$	set of aligned graphs from all modality at depth- p in DB based alignment, $\bar{\mathbf{G}}^p = \{\bar{\mathbf{G}}_1^p, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{G}}_M^p\}$
$\bar{\mathcal{G}}_m$	set of aligned graphs of modality- m in GW based alignment or
	$\bar{\mathcal{G}}_m = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^p$ as the averaged aligned graphs of modality- m across P depths in DB based alignment
$\bar{\mathbb{G}}$	set of all aligned graphs from M modalities, $\bar{\mathbb{G}} = \{\bar{\mathcal{G}}_1, \dots, \bar{\mathcal{G}}_M\}$

than or equal to p from the root node v , and from edges connecting nodes on the identified shortest path in the original graph. Here, Shannon entropy is calculated as:

$$H_s(\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}) = \sum_{u \in (\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p})} -P(u) \log_2(P(u)) \quad (1)$$

where $P(u)$ is the probability of random walk passing through node- u , $P(u) = d(u) / \sum_{a \in \mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}} d(a)$, $d(u)$ is the degree of node- u in the subgraph (Bai et al., 2015). Next, we stack DB vectors of all nodes to construct a DB representation matrix for each graph in modality- m , and repeat the same process for all graphs across all modalities. Differently from (Bai et al., 2019), we propose to add extra depth coefficients (α_m) for different modalities to fairly adjust the amount of subgraph expansions so that for a chosen P value the graph of any modality can be covered at most in P steps and the depth of $\alpha_m P$ mostly covers \mathbf{G}_m^i from any root node v . Hence, we use multiples of α_m (up to $P\alpha_m$) instead of a particular depth value p . The way of calculating depth coefficients will be explained in the Results section. Another difference is that we set DB (i.e., depth-based representation) vector features to 1 in the cases where we cannot cover any node in first depth levels (especially $p=1$) since the depth-based vector representation extraction strategy proposed in (Bai et al., 2019) cannot yield a numerical value for an isolated-point graph (i.e., graph of single node with no edge). Also, in order to eliminate scale difference resulting from the different dimensionalities (i.e., number of nodes in a graph of modality- m), we normalize each DB vector using the following formula:

$$\delta'(v_m) = \frac{\delta(v_m) - 1}{\log_2(n_m) - 1} + 1 \quad (2)$$

In doing so, we substantially remove the heterogeneity of multimodal data. Notice that all DB features for a node in modality- m , which were previously in the range $[1, \log_2(n_m)]$ are now bounded by a lower and upper limit of $[1, 2]$. The algorithm 1 summarizes how DB connectomic features are generated

from the graphs.

Algorithm 1: DB vector extraction

Data: Original brain graph of modality- m (\mathbf{G}_m^i) with size $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times n_m}$, predetermined depth coefficient α_m of modality- m , maximum depth level P .

Result: Extracted DB feature matrix \mathbf{F}' of $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times P}$, where row- v corresponds to v -th DB vector ($\delta(v)$) for node $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^i$

begin

```

    /* Initialization */
     $\mathbf{F} \leftarrow$  create an empty feature matrix of  $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times P}$ 
    /* for each node in the graph  $\mathbf{G}_m^i$  */
    for  $v = 1$  to  $n_m$  do
         $\delta_v \leftarrow$  empty feature vector with  $\mathbb{R}^P$ 
        /* for each depth level- $p$  */
        for  $p = 1$  to  $P$  do
             $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p} \leftarrow$  subgraph rooted at node- $v$ , limited with depth
            amount  $\alpha_m \cdot p$ 
             $\mathbf{H}_s \leftarrow - \sum_{u \in (\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p})} P(u) \log_2(P(u))$ , where
             $P(u) = d(u) / \sum_{a \in \mathbf{G}_{m,v}^{i,p}} d(a)$ 
             $\delta_v[p] \leftarrow$  put  $\mathbf{H}_s$  to  $p$ -th index of  $\delta_v$ 
         $\mathbf{F}[v] \leftarrow$  put  $\delta_v$  to  $v$ -th index row of  $\mathbf{F}$ 
     $\mathbf{F}' \leftarrow 1 + (\mathbf{F} - 1) / (\log_2(n_m) - 1)$  /* normalizing  $F$  w.r.t  $n_m$  */

```

Graph-wave (GW) structural node embeddings. Extracting graph-wave embedding vectors involves node-based graph diffusion to capture the topology of each node neighborhood. We utilize a state-of-the-art model proposed in (Donnat et al., 2018) to extract GW node embeddings. The proposed graph diffusion-based embedding of nodes can successfully differentiate between nodes having different structural local neighborhoods, called *roles* (Donnat et al., 2018). Instead of characterizing the nodes based on depths as in the case of DB representation, graph-wave uses heat diffusion wavelets to discover the structure of the local node topologies (e.g, roles). The method starts with finding unnormalized graph Laplacian of a graph \mathbf{G}_m^i of a modality- m as $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{G}_m^i - \mathbf{D}_m^i$, where \mathbf{D}_m^i is the degree matrix of \mathbf{G}_m^i . Then, we decompose \mathbf{L} into its eigenvector \mathbf{U} and eigenvalue $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ matrix as $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$, where $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n_m})$, assuming

$\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_{n_m}$. The next step is to compute the spectral graph wavelet coefficient matrix as:

$$\Psi = \mathbf{U}g_s(\Lambda)\mathbf{U}^T \quad (3)$$

$g_s(\lambda)$ is the *filter kernel function* described as $g_s(\lambda) = e^{-s\lambda}$ and s is a scale parameter that adjusts the diffusion amount in the network. s is a value in the range $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$, where s_{min} and s_{max} are set to $-\log(0.95)/\sqrt{\lambda_2\lambda_{n_m}}$ and $-\log(0.85)/\sqrt{\lambda_2\lambda_{n_m}}$, respectively. Spectral graph wavelet for node- v , Ψ_v , is the signal as a result of the modulation in the spectral domain of Dirac signal centered around node- v (Donnat et al., 2018). In fact, Ψ_v is the v -th column vector of the spectral graph wavelet Ψ . Moreover, Ψ_{uv} (e.g., the u -th coefficient of Ψ_v) is the amount of heat energy that flows from node- u to node- v . For a given time point t , the characteristic function associated with node- v is formalized as follows:

$$\phi_v(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{u=1}^{n_m} e^{jt\Psi_{uv}} \quad (4)$$

We extract the structural node embedding χ_v for node- v by computing its characteristic function at d evenly sampled time points and concatenating them. Specifically, for time point $t \in (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_d)$, the function evaluated at t ($\phi_v(t)$) is broken down to its real and imaginary parts as $[Re(\phi_v(t)), Im(\phi_v(t))]$ which define the elements of the embedding vector of node- v . We denote the embedded feature vector χ_v for node- v as $[Re(\phi_v(t_i)), Im(\phi_v(t_i))]_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_d}$ (Donnat et al., 2018). The dimension of the embedding χ_v is \mathbb{R}^P , $P = 2d$. It is crucial at this point to standardize the feature matrices by applying standard scaling (e.g., *Z-score Normalization*), since different modalities have different distributions in feature domain. Finally, we repeat the same steps for all nodes in the graph \mathbf{G}_m^i . The steps of finding graph-wave feature embedding are also shown in the algorithm 2

(Donnat et al., 2018).

Algorithm 2: GW vector embedding extraction

Data: Original brain graph of modality- m (\mathbf{G}_m^i) with size $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times n_m}$,
 precalculated scaling factor \mathbf{s} , evenly spaced time points
 $\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_d\}$.

Result: Extracted GW feature matrix \mathbf{F} of $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times 2d}$, where row- v
 corresponds to v -th GW vector ($\delta(v)$) for node $\mathbf{G}_{m,v}^i$

```

begin
  /* Initialization */
   $\mathbf{F} \leftarrow$  create an empty feature matrix of  $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times 2d}$ 
   $\mathbf{L} \leftarrow \mathbf{G}_m^i - \mathbf{D}_m^i$ 
   $\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{\Lambda} \leftarrow$  decompose  $\mathbf{L}$  to eigenvector/eigenvalue matrices
  ( $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$ )
  /* Spectral Graph Wavelet */
   $\Psi \leftarrow \mathbf{U}\mathbf{g}_s(\mathbf{\Lambda})\mathbf{U}^T$ , where  $\mathbf{g}_s(\lambda) = e^{-s\lambda}$ 
  /* for each time point  $t$  */
  for  $t \in \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_d\}$  do
    /* Characteristic function */
     $\Phi(t) \leftarrow$  column-wise mean of  $e^{jt\Psi}$ 
    /* for each node in the graph  $\mathbf{G}_m^i$  */
    for  $v = 1$  to  $n_m$  do
      append [ $Re(\Phi_v(t)), Im(\Phi_v(t))$ ] to current empty fields in
       $v$ -th row of  $\mathbf{F}$ 
  end for
end

```

2.2. Estimation of the alignment template graph

In this step, we use the feature vectors obtained from the previous step to construct correspondence matrices. A correspondence matrix is a table matrix which carries the membership information of the graph nodes (i.e., ROI) specifying which nodes are aligned to which template nodes (e.g, cluster centroids). Specifically, the j -th row and k -th column of a correspondence matrix encodes whether or not a node- j belongs to the cluster k in the hard-version correspondence (i.e., 1 for belonging or 0 for not belonging), or to which extent node- j belongs to cluster centroid- k in the soft-version correspondence (i.e., a probability value between 0 and 1). To do that, for each graph of a modality- m , we create a distance matrix that encodes pairwise dissimilarities between nodes of an original connectome (i.e., ROI)

and a cluster centroids (i.e., nodes of the graph template). Since the feature vectors tell us about the node characteristics, thus the similarity between the nodes, they allow us to categorize the nodes into K groups based on their intrinsic properties (i.e., local structure in the network). Depending upon the version of the alignment strategy (i.e., DB or GW based alignment), we have two ways to implement this task with small differences as we stated earlier.

Clustering DB vectors and constructing correspondence matrices. In this step, we concatenate the depth-based representation vectors of all modalities (i.e., as a single long matrix Δ) and cluster them into n_t groups based on their local similarities, using K-means, which handles the problem of multimodal data heterogeneity. By doing so, we find similar nodes within as well as between-modalities. But to be able to cluster all nodes with respect to different depth values p , at each iteration we use only the first p features (i.e., columns) of Δ in clustering, where p ranges from 1 to P , which allows us to focus on local neighborhoods of different radii. Next, we find n_t clusters and the associated cluster centers. These centers are the best representative vectors that will define the new nodes of the alignment template graph \mathcal{T}^p at depth p . Next, considering the proximity to the cluster centers (i.e., j -th row is k -th column in the distance matrices), we produce correspondence matrices $\{\mathbf{C}^p\}_{p=1}^P$ for graphs from all modalities in \mathbb{G} , whose rows represent the original nodes to be aligned and the columns represent the cluster centers to which the original nodes are aligned.

In hard correspondence version, if a node j belongs to a cluster k (i.e., the closest center to node j is k , or in other words, $\mathbf{A}(j, k)$ is the smallest in the row- j), then $\mathbf{C}(j, k)$ is 1 and every other element in the j -th row in $\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p}$ is set to zero (algorithm 3). On the other hand, in soft correspondence, the correspondence weight of a node- j is distributed between clusters to be inversely proportional to its distances to all cluster centroids, meaning node- j does not entirely belong to a particular cluster. In fact, the assignment of a node- j to each cluster centroid is proportional to the values of an exponential decay function at those distance values (e.g., $C(j, k) \sim e^{-A(j,k)/p}$). The algorithm 4 illustrates how to produce correspondence matrices using soft correspondence. Here, the key point is that the correspondence weights in a row of a correspondence matrix sums up to 1 in both hard and soft cases. Therefore, the sum of the edge weights of a graph following its alignment to the estimated template is preserved in both strategies. Ultimately, we construct our template graph \mathcal{T}^p with dimension $\mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$, where the nodes

are the cluster centroids and the edge weights denote the similarity between each pair of nodes (v,u) calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{T}^p(v, u) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|v - u\|_2}{p}\right) \quad (5)$$

Notice that we apply the same process at all depth values. Eventually, for each depth value p , we have correspondence matrices of all modalities ($m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$), each with $\mathbb{R}^{N_m \times n_m \times n_t}$. These will be used in the next step to align the original multi-modal graphs in \mathbb{G} to each depth-specific template, respectively, thereby producing *aligned* fixed-sized graphs.

Clustering GW vectors and constructing correspondence matrices. The steps in graph-wave version are exactly the same as those of the DB version except that we do not have depths associated with the radius of local neighborhoods, thus multiple extraction of a graph’s corresponding matrices linked to its depths (i.e., $\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p}$). Instead, the coefficients of the extracted graph-wave feature embeddings hold the energy/heat diffusion information of nodes over time. Therefore, we do not need to consider each first p coefficients of the features in each iteration for clustering GW features unlike depths in DB-based alignment. The computation of distance matrices (i.e., A) and correspondence matrices with hard and soft version implementations applies to GW based alignment as well.

Algorithm 3: Hard correspondence matrix

Data: Distance matrix \mathbf{A}_m^i of graph \mathbf{G}_m^i .

Result: associated **hard** correspondence matrix \mathbf{C}_m^i for graph \mathbf{G}_m^i

begin

/* Initialization	*/
$\mathbf{C}_m^i \leftarrow$ create an empty correspondence matrix of $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times n_t}$	
/* for each row (i.e, node) in \mathbf{A}_m^i	*/
for $j = 1$ to n_m do	
$k \leftarrow$ index of the smallest distance in the j -th row of \mathbf{A}_m^i	
put 1 to $\mathbf{C}_m^i[j, k]$ and 0 elsewhere in that row of \mathbf{C}_m^i	

Algorithm 4: Soft correspondence matrix

Data: Distance matrix \mathbf{A}_m^i of graph \mathbf{G}_m^i .

Result: associated **soft** correspondence matrix \mathbf{C}_m^i for graph \mathbf{G}_m^i

begin

```
    /* Initialization */
     $\mathbf{C}_m^i \leftarrow$  create an empty correspondence matrix of  $\mathbb{R}^{n_m \times n_t}$ 
     $\mathbf{S}_m^i \leftarrow e^{-\mathbf{A}_m^i/p}$ 
    /* for each row (i.e, node) in  $\mathbf{S}_m^i$  */
    for  $j = 1$  to  $n_m$  do
        row-sum  $\leftarrow$  sum of the values in row- $j$  of  $\mathbf{S}_m^i$ 
        /* for each centroid */
        for  $k = 1$  to  $n_t$  do
            /* normalization */
             $\mathbf{C}_m^i[j, k] \leftarrow \mathbf{S}_m^i[j, k] / \text{row-sum}$ 
```

2.3. Alignment of multi-modal multi-sized graphs

The first two steps are pivotal for constructing *depth-specific* correspondence matrices $\{\mathbf{C}^p\}_{p=1}^P$ in DB based alignment or a regular correspondence matrices \mathcal{C} in GW based alignment. In this stage, we transform the training multi-modal multi-sized graphs to a set of *unimodal graphs with a fixed size*. In other words, we represent the graphs of arbitrary size with new graphs that have a lower number of nodes which solves the problem of the graph size difference.

DB based graph alignment. For each depth p , modality m and graph i , we learn an associated correspondence matrix from the previous step ($\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p}$) that specifies which nodes in the graph $\mathbf{G}_m^{i,p}$ are to cluster together. Thus, we align each graph i in each modality m using the following *depth-specific* transformation:

$$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^{i,p} = (\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p})^T \times \mathbf{G}_m^i \times (\mathbf{C}_m^{i,p}) \quad (6)$$

One can prove that this simply creates new nodes and edges by combining the original nodes in the same clusters and summing up the connections (i.e., edge weights) from the nodes in cluster i to the nodes in cluster j ($i, j =$

1, 2, \dots, n_m). This can be summarized as $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^{i,p}(j, k) = \sum_{v \in c_j} \sum_{u \in c_k} \mathbf{G}_m^i(v, u)$, where v and u are the nodes in clusters c_j and c_k . At this point, we further propose to normalize the aligned graphs based on the size n_m of the graph in modality m . This is because connectomic modalities larger in size result in more inflated values in aligned graph matrices, and this causes a scaling issue during the classification stage. Specifically, we define the normalization factor (i.e., reduction ratio) as $R_m = (n_t)^2 / (n_m)^2$. Next, for each aligned graph $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^{i,p}$ at different depth values $\{p\}_{p=1}^P$, we average them across depths to produce the final aligned graph $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^i$ of subject i .

$$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^i = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^{i,p} \quad (7)$$

Finally, we use the training set of aligned fixed-sized graphs ($\bar{\mathcal{G}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\bar{N} \times n_t \times n_t}$), where $\bar{N} = \sum_{m=1}^M N_m$, to train a single classifier.

GW based graph alignment. Graph alignment process in GW based alignment is similar to that of DB based alignment. However, since there are no multiple correspondence matrices generated using different depths, we align each graph \mathbf{G}_m^i of any modality *once* with respect to its *entire* extracted feature matrix \mathbf{C}_m^i without averaging aligned graphs.

$$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^i = (\mathbf{C}_m^i)^T \times \mathbf{G}_m^i \times (\mathbf{C}_m^i) \quad (8)$$

The interpretation of new nodes and edges in the aligned graph $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^i$ and the normalization with a reduction ratio R_m are the same as explained in the DB-based alignment.

2.4. Dimensionality reduction with LDA and classification of aligned graphs

Given the aligned graphs ($\bar{\mathcal{G}}$), we aim to classify them into the available brain states $s \in \mathcal{S}$ (i.e., two classes or more). Note that since the aligned graphs are now isomorphic (i.e., having the same size) regardless of their original modalities, it enables us to train a single unified classification model on the aligned data that consists of new fixed-sized graphs with size $\mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$ after vectorization. In particular, we vectorize each aligned brain graph by taking the connectivity weights in the off-diagonal upper triangular part of its adjacency matrix as it is symmetric. Also note that all aligned graphs from

different modalities need not to be paired, thereby alleviating the constraint of training classifiers using paired connectomes derived from two neuroimaging modalities or more. In the testing stage, given a testing brain graph draw from a particular modality, we extract its embedding (i.e., DB or GW vector) followed by a correspondence matrix construction using centroids in \mathcal{T} for alignment. However, prior to the classification step, we propose to apply linear discriminant analysis (LDA), a supervised projection-based dimensionality reduction technique, to the newly created unified multi-modal connectivity vectors. The reason why we use LDA after graph alignment operation is that it not only solves the domain shift problem between modalities in high-dimensional feature space, but also eliminates the heterogeneity of the aligned multi-modal graphs.

Figure 4 illustrates the necessity of LDA and how to apply it to an aligned dataset with 3 modalities. The first step is to vectorize all aligned connectomes as previously explained. Therefore, for each aligned modality, we will have data matrix \mathbf{X}_m of size $\mathbb{R}^{N_m \times f}$, where $f = n_t(n_t - 1)/2$ and each row denotes the vectorized aligned graph $\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m^i$. Next, we independently build LDA models for each modality (\mathbf{X}_m). Note that LDA tries to find a one dimensional projection line so as to maximize the class separation by fitting Gaussian distribution models to the data classes (Fisher, 1936). Upon learning LDA model parameters from the training set \mathbf{X}_m^{tr} , we transform the data matrix \mathbf{X}_m by projecting it onto a 1-D line and normalizing it with standard scaling to get the final data matrix $\bar{\mathbf{X}}_m$ with dimension $\mathbb{R}^{N_m \times 1}$. We repeat the same process for all aligned modalities ($\bar{\mathbf{G}}_m$) and combine the resulting data matrices to get a single homogeneous unimodal data matrix \mathbb{X} of size $\mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$, where N is the total number of graphs from all modalities. Now, we can input \mathbb{X} to the classification block (e.g., linear SVM). The steps of the dimensionality reduction with LDA are summarized in Algorithm 5.

Figure 4: *Steps of proposed dimensionality reduction using LDA.* **1)** Heterogeneous aligned multi-modal graphs. The aligned graphs from different modalities have different distributions and orientations in terms of class boundaries in the feature space. Also it can be easily seen that different modalities cause the overall unified dataset to have a domain fracture, thus a heterogeneous structure, which makes the learning of a simple linear classification model nearly impossible. **2)** Dimensionality reduction with LDA. Therefore, we project each aligned modality dataset to a one-dimensional (1-D) feature space using LDA. **3)** Multi-modal data superimposition. As a last step, after separately applying the standard-scaling (Z-score) to 1-D samples from each modality, we finally superimpose those samples in 1-D feature space before passing them on to the brain state classifier.

Algorithm 5: Dimensionality reduction with LDA

Data: Set $\bar{\mathbb{G}}$ of all aligned graphs, $\bar{\mathbb{G}} = \{\bar{\mathcal{G}}_1, \dots, \bar{\mathcal{G}}_M\}$

Result: Reduced data matrices \mathbb{X}^{tr} and \mathbb{X}^{ts}

begin

```
    /* Initialization */
     $\mathbb{X}^{tr}, \mathbb{X}^{ts} \leftarrow$  empty train and test matrices
    /* for each  $\bar{\mathcal{G}}_m$  */
    for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
         $\mathbf{X}_m \leftarrow$  vectorize( $\bar{\mathcal{G}}_m$ )
         $\mathbf{X}_m^{tr}, \mathbf{X}_m^{ts} \leftarrow$  split-to-train-test( $\mathbf{X}_m$ )
        /* Dimensionality Reduction */
         $\mathbf{M}_{LDA} \leftarrow$  get-LDA-model( $\mathbf{X}_m^{tr}$ )
         $\mathcal{X}_m^{tr} \leftarrow$  dim-reduction-with-LDA( $\mathbf{X}_m^{tr}, \mathbf{M}_{LDA}$ )
         $\mathcal{X}_m^{ts} \leftarrow$  dim-reduction-with-LDA( $\mathbf{X}_m^{ts}, \mathbf{M}_{LDA}$ )
        /* Standard Scaling (Z-score) */
         $\mathbf{M}_s \leftarrow$  get-scaling-model( $\mathcal{X}_m^{tr}$ )
         $\bar{\mathcal{X}}_m^{tr} \leftarrow$  standard-scaling( $\mathcal{X}_m^{tr}, \mathbf{M}_s$ )
         $\bar{\mathcal{X}}_m^{ts} \leftarrow$  standard-scaling( $\mathcal{X}_m^{ts}, \mathbf{M}_s$ )
        concatenate  $\bar{\mathcal{X}}_m^{tr}$  to  $\mathbb{X}^{tr}$ 
        concatenate  $\bar{\mathcal{X}}_m^{ts}$  to  $\mathbb{X}^{ts}$ 
```

3. Results

Multimodal connectomic datasets. To evaluate our method, we use $M = 2$ connectomic datasets:

- F dataset. The functional brain connectivity dataset is derived from resting-state fMRI composed of $N_1 = 517$ subjects with 245 autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and 272 normal controls (NC), each with $n_1 = 116$ ROIs. we used the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) preprocessed public dataset ¹. Several preprocessing steps were implemented by the data processing assistant for resting-state fMRI (DPARSF) pipeline which is based on statistical parametric maps (SPM) and resting-state fMRI data analysis toolkit (REST). First, to

¹<http://preprocessed-connectomes-project.org/abide/>

ensure a steady signal, the first 10 volumes of rs-fMRI images were discarded. Based on a six-parameter (rigid body), all images were slice timing corrected and were realigned to the middle to cut down on inter-scan head motion (Tang et al., 2018). Then, the functional data were registered in montreal neurological institute (MNI) space with a resolution of $3 \times 3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$. To improve signal to noise ratio, spatial smoothing were then applied with a Gaussian kernel of 6 mm. Finally, band-pass filtering (0.01-0.1 Hz) was performed on the time series of each voxel (Price et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2017). These steps are detailed in this link: <http://preprocessed-connectomes-project.org/abide/>. Each brain rfMRI was partitioned into 116 ROIs.

- *M* dataset. The morphological brain connectivity dataset is derived from T1-weighted MRI using cortical attribute of maximum principal curvature comprising $N_2 = 341$ subjects with 155 ASD and 186 NC subjects, each with $n_2 = 35$ ROIs. We used the T1-weighted MRIs in a subpopulation of the ABIDE dataset to derive a morphological brain network for each subject using the processing pipeline introduced in (Mahjoub et al., 2018; Nebli and Rekik, 2019; Dhifallah et al., 2020). Specifically, we used FreeSurfer processing pipeline (Fischl, 2012) to ultimately derive both left and right morphological brain networks. We first constructed both left and right hemispheric surfaces then we parcellated each cortical surface into 35 regions using Desikan-Killiany atlas (Desikan et al., 2006). For each cortical region, we averaged the cortical thickness across its vertices. Next, we computed the absolute difference in average cortical thickness between each pair of cortical regions. Therefore, for each hemisphere of each subject, at each time-point, we produced a 35×35 morphological connectivity matrix (i.e., morphological network).

Preprocessing and parameter setting. The distribution of brain connectivity values (i.e., edge weights) in each original dataset (i.e., F and M) before any preprocessing is shown in Figure 5. We notice a large variations in the shapes that both distributions take, thereby highlighting the data heterogeneity as well as domain fracture between morphological and functional connectomes. As preprocessing steps, we applied thresholding and edge remapping operations to both *F* and *M* datasets. First, we removed the negative and low correlations (i.e., edges) in the functional brain graphs and very low

dissimilarities in the morphological brain networks with threshold values of $\tau_f = 0.1$ and $\tau_m = 0.03$, respectively ($\tau_m = \mu - 0.7 \times \sigma$, where μ and σ denote the mean and standard deviation of the edge weights distribution of morphological brain graphs, respectively). Besides, noting that both modalities are derived from contrasting measures (i.e., Pearson correlation for F and absolute distance for M), we transformed the functional matrices to ‘dissimilarity’ matrices using the weight remapping function $\omega' = 1 - \log_{10}(9 \cdot \omega + 1)$, where ω and ω' are original and new weight of an edge, respectively. The function takes a similarity range $[0 - 1]$ and returns a dissimilarity range $[0 - 1]$, but it maps the higher correlations ($w \approx 1$) to lower distances ($w' \approx 0$) and vice versa. As for morphological brain graphs, we simply stretched their distribution to $[0 - 1]$. For the maximum depth value $P = 5$ in DB based alignment, using grid search, we empirically set the depth coefficients α_f to 0.251 and α_m to 0.14 for functional and morphological brain connectomes, respectively. As such, we can cover shortest paths in graphs of both modalities in approximately P steps. Also for the filter kernel $g_s(\lambda)$ in GW based alignment, within the specified range determined by s_{min} and s_{max} , we chose s as $-\log(0.9)/\sqrt{\lambda_2 \lambda_{n_m}}$, where λ_2 and λ_{n_m} are the second and the largest eigenvalue of the unnormalized graph laplacian.

Figure 5: *Distribution of brain connectivity weights of all original connectomes. 1)* Distribution of functional connectomes. **2)** Distribution of morphological connectomes.

Classification and feature selection. We trained a linear support vector machine (SVM) classifier using 5-fold cross-validation on the aligned brain graphs while varying the number of clusters (i.e., template size) $n_t = 15, 20, 25, 30$ ($n_t \leq \min(n_m)$). As stated previously in Section 2, we applied LDA as a supervised feature extraction technique for each modality- m . As for the traditional classifiers separately trained on each modality (i.e., F or M), to avoid the curse of dimensionality, we leverage the original connectomes

$(n_m \times n_m)$ to identify brain state-specific (or class-specific) discriminative connectivities. To do so, we used two different graph fusion techniques: one is linear averaging, and the second one is non-linear similarity network fusion (SNF) technique proposed in (Wang et al., 2014). SNF fuses a set of graphs by non-linearly diffusing one across the remaining ones in an iterative manner. Given the fused graphs in each class, we compute a residual error matrix by simply taking the absolute difference between both graphs (i.e., adjacency matrices). Next, we select the top K features with highest values in the residual matrix for SVM training and testing. As such we are using the deviation of each brain graph from the class-specific population center as new representation of each subject.

Benchmarking. We benchmarked our method against classification models (i.e., SVM) trained on functional and morphological datasets, independently. Figures 6,7 and 8 display the classification accuracy, sensitivity and specificity scores by the three models for $n_t = 15, 20, 25, 30$, respectively. “UMC” (Unified Multi-modal Connectomes) denotes the joint unified model trained on the combination of the aligned functional and aligned morphological brain networks. “ F ” and “ M ” represent the single models independently trained on the original functional and morphological brain networks without any alignment procedure. For the unified models (i.e., UMC), we applied LDA to the aligned connectomes using their DB or GW node embeddings, respectively, along with a hard or soft correspondence implementation. For each individual classification model (i.e., F and M), we chose the first $K = 15, 20, 25, 30$ discriminative features using SNF and averaging methods, and reported the average classification results. Note that since “ F ” and “ M ” do not depend on n_t values, their accuracies are unchanged in all subplots.

As we can see from Figures 6,7 and 8 that our UMC method achieved highly comparable classification performance with the independent “ F ” and “ M ” models. In particular, our method achieved the best accuracy (53.73%) in $n_t = 20$ with DB based alignment and soft correspondence, which outperforms M with SNF. Moreover, in sensitivity, the best score (50.9%) is obtained in $n_t = 30$ using DB based alignment with hard correspondence. Our model reached the same sensitivities as the F model and outperformed the M model, regardless of the feature selection strategy (i.e., SNF or averaging). As for the specificity, our unified model has the best scores (61.72%, 61.03%) using DB-based alignment with soft correspondence in $n_t = 15, 20$, which largely exceed the specificity of the F model using averaging (56.74%). All in all, DB-based alignment seems slightly more optimistic in classifying unified

multi-modal connectomes compared to GW based alignment, although DB feature vectors have length $P = 5$ and GW embeddings have length $P = 40$ in our experiment. Furthermore, we can say that the scores are boosted with larger template size n_t . That is because we lose less connectomic information using larger n_t template graph size.

Figure 6: Classification accuracies of autistic subjects with alignment template graph sizes $n_t = 15, 20, 25, 30$. UMC denotes our unified multi-modal connectomes classification model. We display the classification results using both soft and hard correspondence strategies. We tested our unified model using GW (pink bars) and DB (green bars) graph embeddings. On the other hand, F and M show the conventional individual models that are separately derived from functional and morphological connectomic datasets using two different strategies for integrating aligned brain graphs with a similar brain state to guide the top discriminative feature selection between two brain states (autistic versus healthy): with a prior feature selection option: similarity network fusion (SNF) (Wang et al., 2014) (orange bars) and linear averaging (turquoise bars). We report the average classification accuracy when varying the number of the most discriminative features as follows: $K = 15, 20, 25, 30$. Note that since “ F ” and “ M ” do not depend on n_t values, their accuracies are unchanged in all subplots.

4. Discussion

In this paper, we set out to solve a challenging neurological disorder classification problem where the input brain graphs vary in size and are drawn

Figure 7: Classification sensitivity scores of autistic subjects with alignment template graph sizes $n_t = 15, 20, 25, 30$. The meanings of acronyms and colors are as detailed in the legend of Figure 6.

Figure 8: Classification specificity scores of autistic subjects with alignment template graph sizes $n_t = 15, 20, 25, 30$. The meanings of acronyms and colors are as detailed in the legend of Figure 6.

from different neuroimaging modalities. As a solution, we designed a unified classification model that leverages a graph-based alignment technique to a template graph of a predefined size (i.e., the number of nodes is fixed) using clustering of graph embeddings based on local node depth or diffusion energy. We evaluated our model on functional and morphological brain connectivity datasets and demonstrated the potential of our model in performing as modality-specific classifiers trained on each dataset, independently. In the absence of state-of-the-art methods in building unified classifiers, we have simply compared our method with independent models. In this paper, we aimed to present a proof-of-concept of the possibility of building a universal classification framework of brain connectomes, with the hope to draw the attention of researchers in related fields such as geometric deep learning on graphs (Bronstein et al., 2017; Cao et al., 2020) to address this challenge. Our unified classification model has achieved quite promising results, however, it has a few limitations that we outline below.

Thresholding. We need to find a proper threshold value τ for each modality in hand since thresholding might over-sparsify brain connectomes. This remains an open area of research in the field of network neuroscience. For instance, (Heuvel et al., 2017) used proportional thresholding approach for resting-state fMRI networks. Also, (Garrison et al., 2015) stated that sparsity-based proportional thresholding provides more stable results on functional networks than absolute thresholding.

Remapping function. Since our method makes use of shortest path algorithm in DB-based alignment, this requires transforming similarity metrics used for computing edge weights in graphs to dissimilarity metrics (i.e., distance) before feeding them into the unified classification model. In our case, we heuristically used a remapping function $\omega' = 1 - \log_{10}(9 \cdot \omega + 1)$, which is not proven to be the best ($\omega' = 1 - \omega$ or $\omega' = \exp(-3\omega)$ could be used). Alternative remapping functions can be utilized such as inverse function.

Selection of the maximum depth level P and the depth coefficient α . P , thus α , in DB-based alignment should be properly set in such a way that avoids oversplitting or undersplitting of the maximum shortest paths in a graph into different depth layers. For large P values (e.g, 20), α would be too small for the subgraph expansion process to occur fast enough. Therefore, subgraphs rooted at some nodes in the graph are unable to go beyond the isolated-node graph until reaching a certain depth value (e.g, $P=5$), resulting in the inefficiency of graph alignment. Similarly, if we set P to a small value (e.g, 3), extracted DB features would not reflect the local node neighborhoods

well as a result of insufficient number of expansion subgraphs.

Future directions. Classification task of samples drawn from a unimodal dataset is less more challenging than the classification of multi-sized multi-modal datasets. Hence, in our experiments, we consider the classification accuracies achieved by independent classifier trained on unimodal datasets “ F ” and “ M ” as upper limits for our unified classification task. As the first work tackling such a multi-challenging classification task, our results seem promising given that (i) ASD is a difficult disorder to diagnose (Lynch et al., 2013; Soussia and Rekik, 2017), (ii) we are handling heterogeneous multimodal connectomic datasets, and (iii) the number of samples varies across datasets. In our future work, we aim to translate our machine learning model to a unified graph neural network for classifying brain graphs drawn from *any distribution, any modality, and with any size* while tapping into the nascent field of geometric deep learning (Bronstein et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2019; Cao et al., 2020).

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed the first-ever unified classification model for classifying multi-modal brain graphs with varying sizes using depth-based and graph-wave based alignment to a unified connective template, which eliminates the need to build multiple learners for different modalities and does not require paired graphs across modalities. Our method can also mitigate the problem of data imbalance between classes in unimodal datasets. This work develops the field of network neuroscience along the *joint multi-source multi-modal data* analysis front, which aims to present a unified model for classifying a wide spectrum of brain states leveraging large-scale available datasets. This further calls for designing more advanced unified classification models to unify our understanding of brain structure, function, and morphology as we learn how to better estimate holistic brain state-specific connectivity templates for joint data alignment and discriminative connection identification.

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